

A STUDY ON THE SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES OF SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY, KARNATAKA

Pradeep M. D. ¹

¹ Institute of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India
Orcid ID:0000-0003-2561-4749; Email ID: mdpradeepnair767@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Purpose: The introduce to the sustainable practices of Srinivas University which contributes to the safe environment motivating institutions to adopt eco-friendly moves on daily basis.

Methodology: Case Study conducted with exploratory research methodology by collecting data from University website and other stake holders. The literature is tested with ABCD analysis framework.

Results & Outcome: The study establishes the Institutional Values and describe the implications of sustainable practices for the Universities.

Originality: The Sustainable Green Practices of the Srinivas University is unique by itself and presentations are done based on the understanding of the author based on this study.

Keywords: Social Responsibilities for Sustainability, Green practices in Higher Education, Going green by Universities, Green Innovation, Eco Friendly Campuses, Green Habits and Practices,

1. INTRODUCTION:

Universities should build pollution free campus with sustainable habits and practices [1]. It should concentrate on recycling waste, minimum reliance over non-recyclable sources, eco-friendly structures, conserving energy and green transportation. [2]. Wate conservation through less use, recycling, rain water harvesting need to be carried. Effective waste management, environmental sensitisation and keeping the Green Standard are key moves.

2. RELATED WORKS:

Review of literature through Google Scholar with publications carried between 2015-2022 is carried for the content analysis. The analysis is provided in the Table 1.

Table 1: Related works on Institutional Values and Social Responsibility for Sustainability

Sl. No	Field of Study	Focus	Findings/Observations	References
1	Gender Equity	Impact of Covid	Democratic Governance during pandemic	Oleschuk M. (2020). [3]
2	Gender Equity and Sustainable Goals	Women’s equal access to natural resources	Improve health	Gupta, G. R., et al. (2019). [4]
3	Sustainable Construction Design	Sustainability	Multi-dimentional approach is essential for sustainability	Solaimani, S., & Sedighi, M. (2020). [5]
4	Sustainable	Environment,	Brings competitive	Liu, Z. J., & et

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

	Construction	energy and Sustainability	advantage	al. (2020). [6]
5	Obligation of Universities	Social Responsibility	High engagement	Paunescu, C & et al. (2017). [7].
6	Energy Master Planning	Energy Conservation	Community goals in energy management.	Rao, L. & et al. (2021). [8]
7	Renewable Energy	Carbon Emission	Education reduces the Carbon Emission	Zafar, M. W., & et al. (2020). [9].
8	Sustainable Energy	Usage of renewable energy	Meeting energy problem	Qazi, A., et al. (2019). [10]
9	Degradable Waste Management	Reduction of Conventional energy	Bio gas will replace the usage of conventional energy sources	Katinas, V., & et al. (2019). [11]
10	Composting	Biodegradable Waste	Pellets and Compost is obtained as by products.	Krstic, I. I., & et al. (2018). [12].
11	Bio based Products	Recycling	Can be converted to organic	Wojnowska-Baryła, et al. (2020). [13].
12	Waste Management	Drum filling as best practice	Electrical energy generated from bio degradable waste	Salve, S., & et al. (2021). [14]
13	Plastic Waste	Hazards of Single use Plastics	Biodegradable polymers are the solutions	Narancic, T., & O'Connor, K. E. (2019). [15]
14	Sustainable Land Management	Soil and Water Conservation	Top down to bottom-up methods.	Nigussie, Z., et al.(2018). [16]
15	Water Conservation	Sustainable Behaviour	Time, water efficient devices, skill gap are the barriers	Addo, I. B., & et al. (2018). [17]
16	Water Conservation	Declining surface and ground water	Conserved through behaviour changes	Pani, A., & et al. (2021). [18].
17	Sustainability performance by Universities	Comparison between Universities	Green Universities are Environmentally Friendly	Dagiliūtė, R., & et al. (2018). [19].
18	Eco-friendly strategies	Commitment on Sustainability	Model Sustainability Framework	Biswas, J. K., & Dash, M. C. (2019). [20].
19	Solar Energy	SDG.	Clean and affordable energy source	Obaideen, K., et al. (2021). [21]
20	Solar energy	Impact	Priority on sustainability	Guney, T. (2022). [22]
21	Green Washing	Misleading	Awareness is essential	More, P.V.,

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

		consumers		(2019). [23]
22	Green building Movement in India	Building performance	Separate Building performance evaluators are required	Gupta, R., et al. (2019). [24]
23	Electricity Audit	Power saving fixtures and equipment's	Saves cost and carbon foot print	Getu, B. N., & Attia, H. A. (2016). [25].
24	Environmental Audit	Renewable energy generation	Multi Criteria Decision making on Environmental Audit	Adhikary, P., & et al. (2015). [26].
25	Value focused Assessment	Connecting Sustainability and Performance	Performance evaluation on sustainability	Ribeiro, M. M., et al.(2016). [27]

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE PRACTICE:

- (1) To Study the best practices of Srinivas University to achieve sustainability.
- (2) To know about the concept of Gender Equity
- (3) To know about energy conservation and alternative sources of energy.
- (4) To understand waste management, water conservation and green audits.
- (5) To know the efforts on equal access, inclusivity, sensitisation on environmental issues.
- (6) To review the measures on extra-curricular events and promotion of eco friendly lifestyle.

4. THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABLE BEST PRACTICES :

Universities shall achieve gender equity, water conservation, waste management, going green, green audits, inclusive environment, propagating code of conduct etc. The Ecological issues influence the strategies on building competitive advantage.

5. INSTITUTIONAL SUSTAINABLE VALUES - THE PRACTICE:

Srinivas University aims to develop environmental concerns. Public Sensitisation Programmes to rehabilitate ecological imbalances. Carry Green Practices in the Teaching, Learning and Evaluation. Build 'Inclusive Culture' and 'Gender Equity' through sensitisation programmes. Waste Management and best utilisation of recycled materials. Adopt Sustainable design in Construction. Green Infrastructural Support. Carry energy conservation and energy, green and environmental audits. Adopt 'Green Code of Conduct'. Paper free Office Management System and digitalisation. It incepts generic values such as having sustainable green campuses, green university certification and recognition, adoption of solar power and green standards and sustainable means of transport

6. SUSTAINABLE SOCIAL RESPENSIBILITIES OF SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY - THE PRACTICES :

6.1 Measures initiated for Promoting Gender Equity: The following are the important best practices in this regard.

(1) **Safety and Security:** Self-defence Training sessions are organised. Campus Safety through Surveillance Cameras [28] and Security Staffs, mock drill, sessions on Cyber Crimes and bus for easy commutation.

(2) **Counselling and Mentoring:** With 1:15 Mentor Student Ratio cases are referred to 'Counselling Cells' to maintain the mental health of the learners.

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

(3) **Common Rooms:** Common Lounges facility and waiting rooms are provided with locker facilities.

(4) **Day Care Centre for Children of the Staff:** Day Care Centre with trained staff to engage children in the playful ways and protect them from abuse and problems

(5) **Efforts on Gender Sensitization:** University maintains gender equity in its students ratio by enrolling 1721 female and 2067 male candidates. Inclusive growth of all is the need [29], gender equity in staff ratio, conducts campus based activities, distressed relief & rehabilitation activities, Embedded gender sensitive Curriculum, atomic Research Centres on Gender Equity Areas, Publication of Books, Industry-Academia Collaboration on Skill Development, MoU’s with Stakeholders, Women Scholarship and Financial Assistance, Infrastructural Support, Subsidised Health Care for all, Internal investigation and enquiry of cases on student harassment [30], Social Sensitization Programme, Digitalisation, Faculty Development Programmes, Women sensitive Facilities with women sensitive education [31].

6.2. Sustainable Construction Design: It is sought through the compliance to Building Regulations, ensuring minimize Heat Exposure to Sun and maintenance of Universal Design

6.3. Facilities provided by the Institution for alternate sources of energy and energy conservation measures: University has installed highly productive Solar energy [32] producing 192 KW power per day. Installed Biogas Plant, installed the wheeling to the Grid, Sensor-based energy Conservation, reliance over Power efficient Equipment.

6.4. Facilities in the Institution for the Management of different types of degradable and non-degradable wastes: University carry out Solid Waste Management through multi bin system, Liquid Waste Management by recycling about 400 litres of waste water per day, Biomedical Waste Management, E- Waste Management by making an MoU with Green Impact Foundation Nandila, Puttur, Dakshina Kannada. Built verme compost pits to decompose the food waste and dispose the chemical waste through strict SOP.

6.5 Facilities for Water Conservation: Rain Water Harvesting units are installed to recharge the Borewell/Open Wells, Tanks and Bunds are built, waste water recycling plant is constituted, water distribution system is maintained.

6.6. Green Campus Initiatives of the University: Entry of automobiles is restricted in the campus, usage of bicycles and battery powered vehicles are encouraged, Pedestrian Friendly Pathways are constructed, ban on the Use of Plastics is declared, Landscaping with Trees and Plants is carried, usage of Public Transport is encouraged and green housekeeping is carried.

6.7. Quality Audits on Environment and Energy and Recognitions on Green Campus initiatives: Annual audits are carried and Green Mentors has recognised the University campus as green with platinum rating. Out campus environmental promotion programmes carried is listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Environmental Promotion Activities conducted between 2017-2022

Sl. No	Name of the Programme	Organising Institute	Date	No of Participants
1	Plantation at International Airport Mangalore	IAS	14/8/2018	20
2	Social Service Activity	IMC	3/10/2018	40

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

3	Cleaning Drive	ISSH	26/3/2019	25
4	Green Campus Programme	IMC	22/7/2019	15
5	Vanamahotsava Programme	ISSH	28/08/2019	15
6	Fire and Safety Awareness Programme	IMC	20/9/2019	200
7	Fire Safety Awareness Programme	IHMT	30/9/2019	60
8	Community Outreach Programme	ISSH/SIRRA	18/11/2019	15
9	Cleanliness Drive	ISSH	26/11/2019	15
10	Environmental Day Celebration	IAS	5/5/2021	200
11	Special Lecture on Tobacco Health and Mental Health Risk	ISSH, NIMHANS, Bangalore	12/6/2021	30
12	Special Lecture on Tobacco Health and Mental Health Risk	ISSH, NIMHANS, Bangalore	12/6/2021	30
13	Cycle Awareness Programme	UBA	28/1/2022	150
14	Coconut Shell Craft Making Competition	IAS	31/1/2022	200
15	Yogic Management of Health	ISSH	3/2/2022	60
16	Craft Making	IAS	7/2/2022	200
17	Visit to Waste Management Project, Puttur	ISSH	23/2/2022	45
18	Environment Awareness Drive	IAS	9/3/2022	50
19	Environment Awareness Drive	IAS	9/3/2022	50
20	Environmental Awareness Drive	IAS	11/3/2022	25
21	Swatch Bharat	IMC	20/5/2022	60
22	Malaria Awareness Programme	UBA	28/5/2022	80
23	One day Campaign on Malaria and Dengue	IMC	31/5/2022	200
24	Survey for evolving a Demonstrable Model ward with Citizens Participation for enhanced ULB Services	ISSH	1/6/2022	10
25	World Environmental Day	ICSIS	4/6/2022	35
26	World Environmental Day	IET	6/6/2022	150
27	Webinar on Sustainable	ICIS	13/6/2022	60

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

	Earth Living in Harmony with Nature			
28	Co-Note Sustainable Communities: Coping with Climate Change	Future earth Global Secretariate Hub South Africa	16/6/2022	100
29	Awareness Programme on Environmental Hygiene at Z.P.H.P.School, Malar	UBA, SIRRA, NSS	23/6/2022	40
30	Awareness Programme on Environmental Hygiene at Z.P.H.P. School, Pavoor	UBA, SIRRA	27/6/2022	45

6.8. The efforts of the University to build disabled-friendly, barrier free environment: University has constructed ramps, lifts, ‘Divyangjan’ friendly washrooms, fixtures, disable friendly Signage, assistive technology, Human assistance, reader facility, scribe etc are provided.

6.9. University initiatives in creating an inclusive environment:

Higher education Institution should always focus for transmission in its pedagogies and approaches. Cultural relativism and peaceful coexistence is propagated in the code of conduct of the University. University celebrates all the major festivals such as Onum, Sri Krishna Janmashtami, Holi, Deepavali, Navaratri, Christmas, Ramzan, Ganesh Chaturthi. Admits students across the geographical locations specially 49.78 % of the students from outside Karnataka. Language other than the mother tongue is allowed as an optional paper, ‘French’ is taught, soft skill training is provided, Kannada and Hindi are provided as electives. TOEFEL training is provided to students. Annual Food Fests with multi cuisines, grievance redressal forums, scholarship assistance, transparent recruitment policy is provided. University annually felicitates achievers for their contribution to the Society with A. Shama Rao Best Teachers Award, Best Social Worker Award, Best Business Award and Best Service Award with salutation and cash prize. Subsidised fees Structure for Karnataka Students. Student and Faculty Development Programmes. Yoga-Samskrith Adhyayana & Research Centre facilitate learning Sanskrit language through online mode the University has initiated ‘Srinivas Bharathi-Proficiency Certification’ programme.

6.10. Sensitization of students and employees on the constitutional obligations- values, rights, duties and responsibilities of citizens: The University has incorporated courses on Constitution of India and co-curricular activities are organised to sensitize students [33] [34]. Youngsters are oriented on service. Prepares the youth to fight against hazards and contingencies. The students are propagated on unity and integrity.

6.11. Universities prescribed Code of Conduct for students, teachers, administrators and other staffs and conducts periodic programmes in this regard: Separate code of Conduct is framed for employees, staff and administrators and approved by the Board of Management. Professional ethics programmes are conducted to Students

6.12. Universities efforts to celebrates / organizes National and International Commemorative days, events and festivals: University celebrates Independence Day, Republic Day, Mahatma Gandhi Jayanthi on 2nd October, Children’s Day on November 14th , National

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

Youth Day on 12th January, Teachers Day on 5th September, Senior Citizens Day with the inmates of old age homes, World Physiotherapy Day on September 8, Engineers’ day etc. The international days such as International Yoga Day was celebrated on 21st June, International Women’s Day on 8th March, World Heart Day on 30th September, World Mental Health Day on 12th October, International Cyber Security Day on 30th November, World Radiography Day on 8th November, World No Tobacco Day on May 31st, World Anaesthesia and Operation Theatre Technologist Day on 20th July, World Environment Day on June 5th etc. celebrates Onam, Holy, Christmas, Ramzan and Sri Krishna Janmashtami. ‘Rashtriya Ekta Diwas’ was commemorated.

7. EVIDENCE OF SUCCESS:

7.1. From University Point of View :

- (1) Implemented zero plastic policy in the campuses.
- (2) Zero tolerance on the usage of Tobacco, Alcohol and Narcotic Drugs in the campus.
- (3) Installed Solar Power, Bio Gas, Verme Compost etc.
- (4) Rain Water Harvesting
- (5) implemented energy conservation measures in its operations.
- (6) Installed Energy saving fans and LED lights in the class rooms.
- (7) Developed Green Landscape in the Campus with plants and trees.
- (8) Commemoration of national and international days on environmental concerns.
- (9) Sensitisation of students on ecological concerns.
- (10) Conservation of water through minimizing the usage volume.
- (11) Introduced innovative “Adopt a Plant” programme for the students.
- (12) Increased the dependence over organic fertilisers and pesticides.
- (13) Maintain toxic and dust free environment with lighting and ventilation in the campuses.
- (14) Usage of local materials in the day to day affairs of the University.
- (15) Strict compliance over the Green Policy will bring sustainability in the longer run.
- (16) Encouraged fuel less vehicles in the campus.
- (17) Clean and Hygienic Campus with full time staffs for maintenance.
- (18) Installed Waste Water Recycling Plant with the capacity of 400 litres per day.
- (19) Constituted Sustainable Education Committee (SEC)

8. PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED AND RESOURCES REQUIRED:

The problems encountered during the planning and implementing the practice are Cost involved on Solar Panels, Bio Gas, Rain Water Harvesting Plants, green landscape etc. Converting to LED Power is challenging. Conducting training on sustainability to faculties is a challenge. Decisions by Sustainable Education Committee (SEC) was tough. The Green Assessment and Accreditation cycle carried by the AICTE is time bound. Sensitising students on reduction of usage of water was a real challenge. Fee charged by the Green Audit firms for the audit is an additional burden to the Universities. No common accreditation guidelines issued by the government. Differences are found in the measuring indexes followed by different Universities [35].

9. ABCD LISTING OF HEI VALUES & SUSTAINABLE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES:

The study uses ABCD framework to analyse upon the utilities and constraints of the Sustainable Social Responsibilities of Srinivas University [36].

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

9.1. Advantages: The model encourage sustainable building designs and structures, conserve top soil through green landscapes, brings in eco-friendly Commuting Practices, effective water management, effective waste water conservation, effective energy management and cost control, reduce disposal of Ozone depleting substances, increase the dependability on renewable energy, usage of eco-friendly materials, effective waste management and recycling, increase compliance to Green Policy, reduce Carbon footprint, brings inclusivity in the campus. adoption of organic waste management, tobacco and drug free campus life, facilitated fresh air, ventilation, lighting and toxin free environment and health and hygiene in the campus.

9.2. Benefits: It reduces Carbon emission, control the usage of single use plastics, sensitize students on narcotic substance, reduce power consumption, conserve rain water, reduce water consumption, best use of recycled water, improves quality air, energy conservation, increase the environmental consciousness, ‘Adopt a Plant’ develop love towards the nature, organic fertilisers will protect the nutritional value of the soil, effective waste management, reduce the carbon foot print, brings in inclusivity, culture and tradition of living with the nature and institutional values teach eco-friendly lifestyle.

9.3 Constraints: Initial investment on green products is burden for the private managements. Strict compliance of green policy has limitations. Annual Green Audit is expensive. Deployment of maintenance staff for green products are costly. For the already existing institutions, transformation to sustainable practices requires time. Educating on sustainable social responsibilities is a difficult task. Green Audit proformas and assessment guidelines create stress on new institutions. Non availability of Common Environmental Standards issued by the Government. Lack of funding on sustainable practices. It may give rise to a new way of Corruption in the name of Sustainability.

9.4 Disadvantages: Non availability of Common Environmental Standards for Higher Education Institutions. Every best sustainable best practice is costly. There exists a chance of manipulation of Green Audit reports and Recognitions. Sustainable Social Responsibility is not effective for short period but profitable for long run. Lack of cooperation from the faculties of Government Higher Education Institutions. Reduce the income to Power supply Corporation. It is difficult to realise the complete sensitization of students on eco-friendly practices and habits. Investment by the Management on Sustainable best practice is costly affair. Introducing Green Products to Higher Education Institutions need to be strategized

10. CONCLUSION :

University through going green claims early mover advantages [37]. These measures bring sustainability [38]. This paper establishes the social responsibilities of the Srinivas University Under the Unnat Bharat Abhiyan, a national programme of MHRD and National Service Scheme (NSS) several environmental sensitization programmes are carried in the community. Institutional Values and Social Responsibilities for sustainability is the need of the day. Even though shifting to green is costly but it is advantageous for the long run [39]. University follows an open feedback system to improve its sustainable efforts. Consistent feedback is taken to improve the best practices of the University.

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

REFERENCES:

- [1] Malinverni, L., Schaper, M. M., & Pares, N. (2016). An evaluation-driven design approach to develop learning environments based on full-body interaction. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 64(6), 1337-1360. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [2] Kolb, M., Frohlich, L., & Schmidpeter, R. (2017). Implementing sustainability as the new normal: Responsible management education—from a private business school's perspective. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 15(2), 280-292. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [3] Oleschuk, M. (2020). Gender Equity Considerations for Tenure and Promotion during COVID-19. *Canadian review of sociology- Revue Canadienne de Sociologie*, 57(3), 502–515. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/cars.12295>. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [4] Gupta, G. R., Oomman, N., Grown, C., Conn, K., Hawkes, S., Shawar, Y. R., & Darmstadt, G. L. (2019). Gender equality and gender norms: framing the opportunities for health. *The Lancet*, 393(10190), 2550-2562. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [5] Solaimani, S., & Sedighi, M. (2020). Toward a holistic view on lean sustainable construction: A literature review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 248, 119213. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [6] Liu, Z. J., Pyplacz, P., Ermakova, M., & Konev, P. (2020). Sustainable construction as a competitive advantage. *Sustainability*, 12(15), 5946. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [7] Paunescu, C., Dragan, D., & Gauca, O. (2017). Examining obligations to society for QS Stars best ranked Universities in social responsibility. *Management & Marketing Challenges for the Knowledge Society*, 12(4), 551-570. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [8] Rao, L., Ontiveros, J., Yonkoski, J., Wauthy, J., & Holt, P. (2021). Energy Master Planning for Resilient Public Communities-Best Practices from North American Universities. *ASHRAE Transactions*, 127(1), 660-672. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [9] Zafar, M. W., Shahbaz, M., Sinha, A., Sengupta, T., & Qin, Q. (2020). How renewable energy consumption contribute to environmental quality? The role of education in OECD countries. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 268, 122149. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [10] Qazi, A., Fayaz Hussain, N. A., Rahim, Glenn Hardaker., Daniyal Alghazzawi, Khaled Shaban., Khalid, Haruna. (2019). Towards Sustainable Energy: A Systematic Review of Renewable Energy Sources, Technologies, and Public Opinions. *IEEE Access*, 7(5), 63837-63851. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [11] Katinas, V., Marciukaitis, M., Perednis, E., & Dzenajaviciene, E. F. (2019). Analysis of biodegradable waste use for energy generation in Lithuania. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 101, 559-567. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [12] Krstic, I. I., Radosavljevic, J., Djordjevic, A., Avramovic, D., & Vukadinovic, A. (2018). Composting as a method of biodegradable waste management. *Facta Universitatis Series: Working and Living Environmental Protection*, 15(2), 135-145. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [13] Wojnowska-Baryła, I., Kulikowska, D., & Bernat, K. (2020). Effect of bio-based products on waste management. *Sustainability*, 12(5), 2088. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [14] Salve, S., Shinde, S., & Bhojwani, K. (2021). Drum Composting: A Unique Solution in Environmental Engineering for Biodegradable Waste Management and Electricity Generation. *AMC Indian Journal of Civil Engineering*, 4(1), 39-45. [Google Scholar↗](#)

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

- [15] Narancic, T., & O'Connor, K. E. (2019). Plastic Waste as a Global Challenge: Are Biodegradable Plastics the answer to the Plastic Waste Problem?. *Microbiology*, 165(2), 129-137. [Google Scholar](#)
- [16] Nigussie, Z., Tsunekawa, A., Haregeweyn, N., Adgo, E., Cochrane, L., Floquet, A., & Abele, S. (2018). Applying Ostrom’s institutional analysis and development framework to soil and water conservation activities in north-western Ethiopia. *Land use policy*, 71, 1-10. [Google Scholar](#)
- [17] Addo, I. B., Thoms, M. C., & Parsons, M. (2018). Barriers and drivers of household water-conservation behavior: A profiling approach. *Water*, 10(12), 1794. [Google Scholar](#)
- [18] Pani, A., Ghatak, I., & Mishra, P. (2021). Understanding the Water Conservation and Management in India: An Integrated Study. *Sustainable Water Resources Management*, 7(5), 1-16. [Google Scholar](#)
- [19] Dagiliute, R., Liobikiene, G., & Minelgaite, A. (2018). Sustainability at Universities: Students perceptions from Green and Non-Green Universities. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 181, 473-482. [Google Scholar](#)
- [20] Biswas, J. K., & Dash, M. C. (2019). Building a Green Image: Best Sustainability Practices in Universities. *Science and Culture*.85(5), 308-314. [Google Scholar](#)
- [21] Obaideen, K., AlMallahi, M. N., Alami, A. H., Ramadan, M., Abdelkareem, M. A., Shehata, N., & Olabi, A. G. (2021). On the contribution of solar energy to sustainable developments goals: Case study on Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum Solar Park. *International Journal of Thermofluids*, 12, 100123. [Google Scholar](#)
- [22] Guney, T. (2022). Solar energy and sustainable development: evidence from 35 countries. *International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology*, 29(2), 187-194. [Google Scholar](#)
- [23] More, P. V. (2019). The impact of Greenwashing on Green Brand Trust from an Indian perspective. *Asian Journal of Innovation and Policy*, 8(1), 162-179. [Google Scholar](#)
- [24] Gupta, R., Gregg, M., Manu, S., Vaidya, P., & Dixit, M. (2019). Customized Performance Evaluation Approach for Indian Green Buildings. *Building Research & Information*, 47(1), 56-74. [Google Scholar](#)
- [25] Getu, B. N., & Attia, H. A. (2016). Electricity Audit and reduction of Consumption: Campus Case Study. *IJAER*, 11(6), 4423-4427. [Google Scholar](#)
- [26] Adhikary, P., Roy, P. K., & Mazumdar, A. (2015). ESIA and Environmental Audit for Small Hydro Power Projects–MCDM Approach. *IASH Journal-International Association for Small Hydro*, 4(1), 24-32. [Google Scholar](#)
- [27] Ribeiro, M. M., Hoover, E., Burford, G., Buchebner, J., & Lindenthal, T. (2016). Values as a bridge between sustainability and institutional assessment: A case study from BOKU University. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*. 17(1). 40-53. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-12-2014-0170>. [Google Scholar](#)
- [28] Madhushree, L.M., Pradeep, M.D., & Aithal, P.S. (2019). Boosting Education through Mobile Technology in India – Study with reference to Generation Z. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 3(2), 96-105. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/3597588>. [Google Scholar](#)

One Day National Virtual Conference on “Sustainability and Transformation in Management, Technology, Social Science, Education and Tourism”- AVICON-2022, ISBN: 978-93-94676-04-6

- [29] Pradeep, M. D. (2018). Study on the Mobility in Status of Women Evolutionary Phases towards Empowerment in India. *International Journal of Management, Technology and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 3(2), 73-86. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1462570> [Google Scholar](#)
- [30] Thomas, A. (2015). Incidents of Sexual Harassment at educational institutions in India: Preventive Measures and Grievance Handling. *International Journal of Recent Advances in Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(03), 0317-0322. [Google Scholar](#)
- [31] Pradeep, M. D., & Ravindra B. K. (2017). Review on the Gender Sensitive Women Education-Legal Revolution in Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(1), 53-65. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.821378>. [Google Scholar](#)
- [32] Acharya, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2016). Impact of Green Energy on Global Warming-A Changing Scenario. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1), 838-842. [Google Scholar](#)
- [33] Lata, K. (2016). Right to Healthy Environment and Sustainable Development. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 6(3), 245-251. [Google Scholar](#)
- [34] Bhat, S. A., Zahid, A. T., Sheikh, B. A., & Parrey, S. H. (2017). Environmental education in India: An approach to Sustainable Development. *FIIB Business Review*, 6(1), 14-21. [Google Scholar](#)
- [35] Olcay, G. A., & Bulu, M. (2017). Is measuring the knowledge creation of Universities Possible?: A review of University Rankings. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 123, 153-160. [Google Scholar](#)
- [36] Aithal, P. S. (2017). A critical study on Various Frameworks used to analyse International Business and its Environment. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 1(2), 78-97. [Google Scholar](#)
- [37] Pradeep, M.D., & Akhilesh Suresh, A Kuckian. (2016). Green Marketing to meet Consumer demands and Sustainable Development-Challenges and Opportunities. *International journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology (IJATET)*, 1(1), 34-41. [Google Scholar](#)
- [38] Pradeep, M.D., & Akhilesh Suresh, A Kuckian. (2017). Going Green in Business- A Study on the Eco-friendly initiatives towards Sustainable Development in India. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 1(2), October, 40-50. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1017596>. [Google Scholar](#)
- [39] Yasmin, Begum R., Nadaf., & Shamshuddin, R Nadaf. (2014). Green Marketing: Challenges and Strategies for Indian Companies in 21st century. *IMPACT International Journal of Research in Business Management (IMPACT: IJRBM)*, 2(5), 91-104. [Google Scholar](#)